

Notes

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Chloride Ion by Permanganate Ion

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ALTHOUGH the oxidation of halide ions by permanganate ion has been reported,¹⁻⁶ yet sufficient data regarding kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of chloride ion by permanganate ion are not available. In the present communication, therefore, some results from a detailed study carried out on the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of chloride ion by permanganate ion are put forth.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of either E. Merck (G.R.) quality or B.D.H. Analar quality. The required solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water in pyrex glass vessels, utilising standard methods.

The kinetics were followed by removing aliquots of the reaction mixture at known intervals of time and by quenching the reaction by adding them to a known excess of ice cold water. The diluted reaction solution was estimated by colorimetric method at the absorption maximum of MnO_4^- at 525 nm. The absorbance A_p , due to products was measured and the first order rate constants were found to be insensitive to the exact value of A_p . Plots of $\log(A - A_p)$ vs time were obtained to give straight lines, where $(A - A_p)$ is the net absorption due to MnO_4^- at time t ; which shows that order with respect to permanganate ion is one.

The chloride ion concentration was varied from 0.25M to 0.071M at constant hydrogen ion concentration. Linear plots of $\log k_1$ vs. $\log [Cl^-]$ were obtained, with an average slope, 1.98. This shows that the reaction is second order in chloride ion.

Similarly first order rate constant vs hydrogen ion concentration plot at constant concentration of chloride ions, using different initial concentration of hydrogen ion shows order to be first with respect to hydrogen ion.

Results and Observations

The fourth order rate constant has been calculated and results are summarized in different tables given below :

Arrhenius parameters were determined from the averages of k_4 at different temperatures, the energy of activation and the entropy of activation as

calculated from the experimental results are 18.2 K. Calories per mol and -17.8 e.u. respectively.

TABLE 1—OBSERVED RATE CONSTANTS FOR $Cl^- - MnO_4^-$ REACTION. EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AND CHLORIDE ION CONCENTRATION

Temperature	$[Cl^-]M$	$[MnO_4^-] 10.0 \times 10^{-4}M; [H_2SO_4] 1.5M$		Average $10k_4M^{-3}Min^{-1}$
		$10^2k_1 Min^{-1}$	$10k_4M^{-3}Min^{-1}$	
25°	0.100	1.913	12.76	—
"	0.083	1.468	14.10	13.49
"	0.071	1.030	13.61	—
30°	0.100	3.483	23.22	—
"	0.083	2.532	24.32	23.48
"	0.071	1.732	22.91	—
35°	0.100	5.227	34.85	—
"	0.083	3.636	34.92	35.10
"	0.071	2.750	35.52	—
40°	0.100	9.123	60.81	—
"	0.083	6.424	61.73	62.12
"	0.071	4.834	63.83	—

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF THE VARIATION OF SULPHURIC ACID CONCENTRATION

$[H_2SO_4]M$	$[MnO_4^-] 10.0 \times 10^{-4}M; [Cl^-] 8.3 \times 10^{-3}M; Temperature 25^\circ$				
	$10^2k_1Min^{-1}$	1.50	1.71	1.92	2.21
	1.470	2.700	4.750	7.220	9.579

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF THE VARIATION OF PERCHLORIC ACID CONCENTRATION

$[HClO_4]$	$[MnO_4^-] 10.0 \times 10^{-4}M; [Cl^-] 8.3 \times 10^{-3}M; Temperature 30^\circ$			
	$10^2k_1Min^{-1}$	1.50	1.75	2.00
	3.766	5.910	8.870	15.030

From the tables 2 and 3 regarding summary of the results for the effect of variation of acid concentrations on the reaction rate, it is evident that, in the case of both sulphuric and perchloric acids, the value of the rate constant increases with the increasing acid concentrations.

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